

Vaccine Trade and Production in Brazil During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Government Strategies and Challenges

*Comércio e Produção de Vacinas no Brasil Durante a Pandemia De
COVID-19: Desafios e Estratégias Governamentais*
*Comercio y Producción de Vacunas en Brasil Durante la Pandemia
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Abstract:

This study analyzes Brazil's strategic actions in the vaccine trade during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the challenges related to vaccine importation, production, and regulation. The health crisis highlighted the importance of vaccination as a key strategy to contain the spread of the virus, while also exposing the country's vulnerability due to limited domestic production and strong dependence on imported inputs. The research adopts a bibliographic methodology based on secondary sources such as academic articles, official documents, and news reports. Its main objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of Brazil's public policies, and the structural challenges faced in dealing with the global health crisis.

Keywords: Vaccines; COVID-19; Importation; Production; Public policy.

Resumo:

Este trabalho analisa as ações estratégicas do Brasil no comércio de vacinas durante a pandemia da covid-19, com ênfase nos desafios enfrentados nos processos de importação, produção e regulamentação. A crise sanitária evidenciou a importância da vacinação como principal estratégia de contenção da propagação do vírus, ao mesmo tempo em que expôs a vulnerabilidade do país, marcada pela escassez na produção nacional de imunizantes e pela alta dependência de insumos importados. A pesquisa, de natureza bibliográfica, baseia-se em fontes secundárias, como artigos acadêmicos, documentos oficiais e reportagens jornalísticas, com o objetivo de oferecer uma visão abrangente das políticas públicas adotadas e dos obstáculos estruturais enfrentados pelo Brasil no enfrentamento da pandemia.

Palavras-chave: Vacinas; Covid-19; Importação; Produção; Políticas públicas.

Resumen:

Este estudio analiza las acciones estratégicas de Brasil en el comercio de vacunas durante la pandemia de la COVID-19, con énfasis en los desafíos relacionados con la importación, producción y regulación de vacunas. La crisis sanitaria evidenció la importancia de la vacunación como estrategia clave para contener la propagación del virus, al tiempo que expuso la vulnerabilidad del país debido a la limitada capacidad de producción nacional y a la fuerte dependencia de insumos importados. La investigación adopta una metodología bibliográfica basada en fuentes secundarias, como artículos académicos, documentos oficiales e informes

periodísticos. Su objetivo principal es ofrecer una visión integral de las políticas públicas adoptadas por Brasil y los desafíos estructurales enfrentados durante la crisis sanitaria global.

Palabras clave: Vacunas; COVID-19; Importación; Producción; Políticas públicas.

1. INTRODUCTION

In March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the COVID-19 pandemic, an acute respiratory infection caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, initially detected in China in December 2019. Classified as a public health emergency of international concern, the pandemic lasted more than three years and had profound consequences across various areas, especially in global health and the economy.

With the exponential increase in the number of infected people, the urgency of emergency solutions to contain the virus's spread also grew. In this scenario, vaccination emerged as one of the most effective strategies for reducing the impact of the pandemic. Thus began a global race for the development, approval, and distribution of vaccines, in a context marked by intense geopolitical disputes and economic inequalities.

The development, production, and international distribution of vaccines, however, presented significant challenges for many countries, especially those with limited infrastructure and less integration into international trade—as is the case with Brazil. This article aims to analyze Brazil's actions regarding vaccine imports and production during the pandemic.

Given this scenario, the question arises: what were the main challenges and impacts of Brazil's policies in the vaccine trade during the COVID-19 pandemic? With a large population and a fragile public health system, the country faced significant difficulties in acquiring and distributing vaccines, compromising its response to the health crisis.

Given that vaccination is an essential tool in combating epidemiological outbreaks, it becomes necessary to understand Brazilian trade policies to gain a broad perspective on the effects of these decisions during critical moments. This is, therefore, one of the specific objectives of this work.

The pandemic-driven health instability led to a global demand for vaccines that quickly exceeded the world's production capacity. In situations like this, countries with greater economic power and political influence tend to make advance agreements with manufacturers, guaranteeing priority access to vaccines. Meanwhile, developing nations, such as Brazil, remain at a disadvantage in negotiations and access to immunizations.

Therefore, this study seeks to identify the main obstacles Brazil faces in acquiring, importing, and producing vaccines, examining everything from initial negotiations to national production strategies. The focus is on the effects of the country's trade and health policies, considering the concrete results of these decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The rationale for this article lies in the need to understand the successes and failures that occurred during a health crisis of historic proportions. The decisions made during this period had direct consequences on the lives of millions of Brazilians. Thus, by critically analyzing this context, we will be better prepared to respond to future emergencies more efficiently and responsibly.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 The Vaccine Trade in the National Territory

The commercialization of vaccines is an essential part of global public health

and involves steps such as production, distribution, and procurement of immunizations against various infectious diseases. In Brazil, this market is complex, combining domestic production with imports, and involves multiple institutional actors to ensure an adequate supply of vaccines to the population.

Vaccine production and distribution in Brazil begin through negotiations with national and international manufacturers. The Unified Health System (SUS) is primarily responsible for receiving and distributing immunizations through national immunization programs managed by the Ministry of Health, in coordination with state and municipal health departments. The National Health Surveillance Agency (ANVISA) is responsible for regulation and oversight, ensuring that all vaccines meet the required safety and efficacy criteria (ANVISA, 2022).

Among the most widely used vaccines in the country are those against yellow fever, hepatitis B, and influenza. The yellow fever vaccine, for example, is produced by the Butantan Institute and the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz) and is widely administered in endemic regions. The hepatitis B vaccine, also manufactured by Fiocruz, is part of the national childhood vaccination schedule. The influenza vaccine, produced annually by the Butantan Institute, is targeted at priority groups, such as the elderly and healthcare professionals (Fiocruz, 2020; Butantan, 2022).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Fiocruz played a strategic role in the national production of the vaccine developed in partnership with AstraZeneca and the University of Oxford (Fiocruz, 2024). Vaccine production in Brazil involves rigorous steps: it begins with research and development (R&D), goes through antigen production, formulation, filling in sterile vials and, finally, a thorough quality control before distribution.

ANVISA is the entity responsible for continuous inspection at all these stages, ensuring that products meet national safety and quality standards (ANVISA, 2023). Despite its significant production capacity, Brazil still heavily depends on the import of inputs—approximately 90% of the raw materials used in vaccine production come from abroad (Ipea, 2024). The entry of these inputs is regulated by ANVISA, with specific rules to guarantee the sanitary safety of the process.

2.1.1 Importation of Inputs for Vaccine Production

The process of importing vaccines and their inputs into Brazil is highly regulated. For products to be approved, they must meet rigorous requirements, such as good manufacturing practice certifications, quality control reports, and adequate transport and storage conditions (ANVISA, n.d.).

During the pandemic, the country implemented exceptional measures to expedite imports. These measures included granting temporary authorizations, reducing bureaucratic barriers, and relaxing documentary requirements to facilitate the entry of vaccines and essential supplies into the national territory (ANVISA, 2023).

The importation of raw materials was also subject to detailed regulation by ANVISA and the Federal Revenue Service. The required documentation includes

certificates of compliance with Brazilian standards and reports proving quality control and proper storage of the raw materials (ANVISA, 2021).

2.1.2 Regulations Related to the Importation of Vaccines in Brazil

Brazilian legislation establishes several rules governing the trade and imports of vaccines, including the customs clearance process. This process involves sanitary inspections conducted by the Federal Revenue Service in conjunction with ANVISA to verify product conformity with current sanitary standards (ANVISA, 2022).

The main laws governing this process are:

- **Law No. 6,360/1976** – Establishes the health surveillance regime for products of interest to health, requiring registration with ANVISA and compliance with technical standards (Brazil, 1976);
- **Law No. 6,437/1977** – Defines the penalties for sanitary infractions, including in the context of imports (Brazil, 1977);
- **Law No. 9,782/1999** – Creates ANVISA and defines its responsibilities (Brazil, 1999);
- **Decree No. 8,077/2013** – Regulates Law No. 9,782/1999 and defines the health surveillance system (Brazil, 2013);
- **Law No. 13.301/2016** – Amends Law No. 8.080/1990, including provisions on immunization actions (Brazil, 2016);
- **Law No. 13.979/2020** – Created to address the COVID-19 pandemic, it authorizes ANVISA to adopt exceptional measures for emergency imports (Brazil, 2020).

Other relevant regulatory instruments include:

- **RDC No. 81/2008** – Establishes requirements for the registration and marketing of vaccines in Brazil;
- **RDC No. 204/2017** – Defines quality standards for vaccine manufacturers;
- **RDC No. 23/2021** – Temporarily authorizes the importation and emergency use of vaccines in public health situations (Brazil, 2021).

In addition to resolutions, ANVISA and the Ministry of Health regularly publish ordinances and normative instructions that update the requirements related to the importation and sanitary control of immunizing agents.

2.2 Brazil's Actions Regarding Vaccine Imports

During the pandemic, Brazil faced several challenges related to the importation and distribution of vaccines, mainly due to high global demand. Like other nations, the country faced the urgent need to acquire vaccines to contain the spread of COVID-19.

In situations of health crisis, such as that caused by the pandemic, special

operations – often adapted or made more flexible – are used to expedite processes. One example was the authorization of imports on an exceptional basis, a procedure that, according to ANVISA (Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency), entails evaluating requests from individuals, companies, and government agencies for situations not covered by the agency's regular regulations. During the pandemic, this mechanism was modified to more effectively meet the country's emergency needs.

These assessments sought to meet urgent demands that exceeded existing regulatory capacity, thereby enabling the simplification and acceleration of the vaccine import process and bringing it closer to the model adopted by the international consortium Covax Facility.

Another measure adopted by the Brazilian government was joining Covax Facility, an initiative coordinated by the World Health Organization (WHO), the Gavi Alliance, and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI). The consortium aims to accelerate the development, production, and equitable distribution of vaccines globally, offering immunizations at cost price to developing countries (Covax Facility, 2021). Among the vaccines included in the initiative were those from Pfizer/BioNTech, AstraZeneca, Janssen, Moderna, Sinopharm, and Sinovac.

Brazil joined the initiative as an investor, announcing an investment of R\$ 2.5 billion to purchase approximately 42 million doses. Despite the significant investment, the number of doses acquired was considered low, prompting criticism of the effectiveness of the country's participation in the initiative. As justification, the federal government prioritized bilateral contracts with laboratories to ensure greater predictability in delivery times and conditions (Savino, 2021).

One example of a relevant bilateral contract was signed between the Ministry of Health and the AstraZeneca laboratory, through the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz), via the Institute of Technology in Immunobiologicals (Bio-Manguinhos). This was the main partnership directly funded by the Brazilian government (Fiocruz, 2020).

The initial supply of vaccines was limited, hindering the immediate implementation of mass vaccination. Faced with this, the government opted to establish priority groups for the initial receipt of doses. These groups included people with chronic diseases—such as obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular, renal, respiratory diseases, and cancer—individuals with hematological diseases, seniors over 60 years of age, and healthcare professionals working on the front lines against COVID-19. Over time, vaccination was extended to other segments of the population until it reached the general public (Domingues, 2021).

2.3 Controversial Behavior in Vaccine Purchases

Considering all the challenges faced during the pandemic, questions arose regarding omissions and negligence by the federal government in its actions to combat COVID-19. One of the initiatives adopted to investigate possible irregularities was the establishment of the Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry

(CPI) on the Pandemic.

According to the Legislative Assembly of the State of São Paulo (ALESP), a Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry (CPI) is one of the instruments used by the Legislative Branch to exercise its oversight function. The commission is created by an act of the president of the legislative body, requiring the signature of at least one-third of the parliamentarians, and its purpose is to investigate specific facts. In the context of the pandemic, the CPI established by the Federal Senate aimed to investigate possible omissions and irregularities committed by the government of then-President Jair Bolsonaro, especially regarding the acquisition and regulation of vaccines (Federal Senate, 2021).

The commission revealed significant flaws in the management of the health crisis, citing delays in government decision-making that exacerbated the pandemic's impact. The CPI's final report indicated negligence by the federal government, with the indictment of several authorities, including President Jair Bolsonaro, accused of crimes such as prevarication and crimes of responsibility. The then Minister of Health, Eduardo Pazuello, was also indicted for omissions and other irregularities.

A notable testimony came from Dimas Covas, director of the Butantan Institute, who told CNN Brazil that the country could have been among the first in the world to begin COVID-19 vaccination if there had been greater speed in the approval and regulation of immunizations. While other nations authorized the emergency use of vaccines as early as 2020, Brazil granted such permission only at the end of that year.

Another controversial point was the Ministry of Health's refusal of three proposals to acquire the Coronavac vaccine, made by the Butantan Institute in 2020. Developed by the Chinese laboratory Sinovac, Coronavac was one of the first immunizing agents available. The rejection of the proposals sparked criticism and raised doubts about the transparency and rationality of the federal government's decisions (Brasil de Fato, 2021).

The slow pace and arbitrary approach to vaccine negotiations and regulations negatively impacted Brazil's response to the pandemic. The delay in initiating mass vaccination contributed to the maintenance of high transmission rates, exacerbating the public health crisis. Furthermore, suspicions of irregularities and a lack of clarity in government decisions undermined public confidence.

Finally, according to an Oxfam report, Brazil faced significant obstacles to equitable access to vaccines, highlighting its external dependence. The fact that the country imports approximately 90% of the raw materials needed for vaccine production demonstrates the fragility of national production and the lack of self-sufficiency in this area.

3. METHOD

This study adopts a bibliographic research approach, analyzing secondary sources to examine the vaccine trade in Brazil, with an emphasis on production,

importation, and regulation.

The choice of this methodology is justified by the need to obtain a broad, contextualized understanding of the country's historical and current vaccine landscape. Empirical methods, such as interviews or questionnaires, were excluded due to the difficulty of obtaining detailed, up-to-date information directly from those involved, as well as the logistical complexity and high costs of this data collection.

The research was conducted through a review and critical analysis of existing literature, encompassing academic articles, official documents from regulatory bodies, relevant legislation, and reports from international organizations. The purpose was to understand the complexity of activities related to the vaccine trade in Brazil, from production processes to importation and regulation, with special attention to the exceptional measures adopted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The research sample consists of secondary-source documents and publications, such as laws, decrees, institutional reports, and studies by research entities. The criteria for selecting sources included thematic relevance and timeliness, with priority given to recent publications and official documents to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the information analyzed.

The analysis was conducted qualitatively, identifying recurring patterns and themes across the consulted sources, thereby highlighting the main information relevant to the object of study.

The main limitation of bibliographic research is its reliance on secondary sources, which may not capture more recent or specific aspects of the constantly evolving landscape. Furthermore, the analysis is contingent upon the availability and accessibility of documents, which can vary in terms of detail and scope of coverage.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study highlights the challenges Brazil faces in importing, producing, and distributing vaccines, as well as the impacts of government decisions on the effectiveness of the response to the COVID-19 health crisis.

One of the main obstacles observed is the high dependence on imported inputs. Approximately 90% of the raw materials used in vaccine production in the country are sourced abroad, making Brazil vulnerable to logistical delays and fluctuations in international markets. This dependence slowed the vaccination process, which could have been significantly more efficient with greater self-sufficiency in national production.

The Brazilian National Health Surveillance Agency (ANVISA), responsible for regulating and overseeing vaccines, implemented several changes to import regulations during the pandemic. Among these changes, the acceleration of approval processes and the reduction of bureaucracy stand out, aimed at facilitating the entry of vaccines into the country. Despite these measures, their

effectiveness has been questioned, as the country continued to face difficulties in coordinating and executing acquisitions.

Another relevant aspect was Brazil's participation in the Covax initiative. The Facility, a global alliance coordinated by the World Health Organization (WHO), Gavi, and CEPI, aims to ensure equitable access to vaccines. The Brazilian government invested R\$ 2.5 billion to acquire approximately 42 million doses, a number considered insufficient to meet the population's needs. This has drawn criticism of the adopted strategy's effectiveness, especially when compared with other countries that have secured significantly larger batches.

Excessive reliance on bilateral contracts also posed a risk. Although this model of direct negotiation with laboratories may offer guarantees such as deadlines and delivery volume, the fragmentation of strategies and the lack of coordination between levels of government compromised the success of the vaccination program. The Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry (CPI) on the Pandemic investigated these shortcomings, showing that delays in acquisitions and inadequate planning negatively impacted public health.

The lack of transparency in government decisions during the pandemic was another factor that contributed to the loss of public trust. The Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry's investigations revealed evidence of negligence, including the rejection of proposals from the Butantan Institute to acquire the Coronavac vaccine early, which could have significantly accelerated vaccination. These refusals, coupled with delays in the authorization of emergency use, fueled frustration and distrust among the public.

Reports from health professionals and public managers indicated consensus on the need for greater clarity in negotiations and decision-making. Many pointed out that a lack of transparency can lead to negative perceptions of the government's ability to respond to health crises. In emergency contexts, public trust is essential for the success of immunization campaigns, and its absence is a risk factor for public adherence (CNN Brasil, 2021).

Among the most relevant lessons drawn from this study, the urgency of investments that promote Brazil's self-sufficiency in vaccine production stands out. The pandemic highlighted the fragility of global supply chains and the vulnerability of systems excessively dependent on imports. Expanding national infrastructure and production capacity should become a strategic priority to ensure greater autonomy in future public health emergencies.

The results indicate that a more structured approach, with advance planning and collaboration between government agencies and private institutions, can mitigate several of the obstacles faced. Coordination between the federal, state, and municipal levels, coupled with strategic partnerships with national and international laboratories, is fundamental to ensuring rapid and equitable access to vaccines in crisis scenarios.

Finally, it should be noted that data analysis can be influenced by external variables, such as international demand for vaccines and priorities established by other countries. Thus, it is concluded that prior planning and global cooperation

are crucial factors in ensuring more effective responses to future pandemics.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Despite having a significant infrastructure for vaccine production, Brazil remains highly dependent on imported supplies, a factor that exposed its vulnerability during the global health crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The scarcity of raw materials and the need for emergency regulations highlighted the fragility of the national health system in the face of large-scale emergencies, aggravated by logistical delays and controversial government decisions, such as the initial rejection of proposals to acquire the Coronavac vaccine.

The study also highlighted the negative impact of federal government actions, especially under the leadership of then-President Jair Bolsonaro. His stance, characterized by omissions, slow decision-making, lack of transparency, and resistance to science, was widely questioned and investigated by the Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry (CPI) on COVID-19. These factors contributed to a disjointed response to the health crisis, with direct consequences for the delay in starting vaccination and the increase in the number of preventable cases and deaths.

Thus, the pandemic highlighted the urgent need to strengthen the national public health system through structural investments to expand domestic vaccine production capacity and modernize regulatory processes. Furthermore, it is essential to adopt more transparent, efficient, and evidence-based governance strategies for decision-making in emergency situations.

Brazil's adherence to the Covax initiative. The establishment of a facility and the signing of bilateral agreements with international pharmaceutical companies reflect efforts to ensure population immunization. However, inequality in global access to vaccines and the prioritization of wealthier countries have compromised the equitable distribution of immunizations, delaying the start of vaccination in developing countries, such as Brazil.

Finally, this study concludes that the Brazilian experience during the COVID-19 pandemic offers important lessons on the importance of self-sufficiency in vaccine production, international cooperation, and responsible public management—fundamental aspects for a more effective response to future health crises.

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